

To be Intelligent or not to be: The Sociocultural Construction of Intelligence in Two Bangladeshi Schools

Abstract

This research explores how sociocultural processes construct intelligence in schools and shape the everyday experiences of students. More specifically, it explores the elements and beliefs that teachers and students associate with intelligence and how classification based on intelligence affects classroom experiences, pedagogy, and student selfhood. Based on the ethnographic fieldwork conducted in two schools of Cumilla district in Bangladesh from July to August 2023, I argue that different categories of elements such as academic success, behaviour, moral trait and communication skills function as the markers of intelligence. In addition to that, I argue that three types of beliefs based on naturalistic, personalistic and supernatural assumptions shape the notion about the source of intelligence in school settings. This research also explores the effect of classification based on intelligence in schools by arguing that this classification affects the selfhood of the students by regulating behaviour and also creates an unequal pedagogical relationship in classes. This article contributes to the field of Educational Anthropology by illuminating the sociocultural construction of intelligence within Bangladeshi schools.

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1. Introduction

Schools are places where competitions based on intelligence are always ongoing and it makes schools a battleground of being intelligent in a variety of ways (Lundqvist, 2019). Different studies show that the idea of intelligence and identity formation linked to intelligence is embedded in the sociocultural realm of society (Hatt, 2012; Sternberg, 2007). Thereby, when the classification based on intelligence is done in the schooling system, the social and cultural processes are latent there, shaping actors in particular settings. Though schools are places for nurturing students, schools worldwide show a similar tendency to measure ‘success’ and ‘failure’ through intelligence, test result competency and many other parameters (Varenne & McDermott, 1999). Those processes of measuring, tagging and classifying students have a wider impact on schools.

The Bangladeshi education system is undergoing significant transformations driven by the inception of new policies, curriculum and evaluation systems in school and college systems (Sarker & Chowdhury, 2018). Many features like teaching and evaluation methods of the education system are often debated, contested and resisted, sometimes leading to political issues. Due to the exam-driven evaluation system in operations (Sarker & Chowdhury, 2018), the measurement of academic success is the constant element of everyday practice in Bangladeshi schools. Intelligence is one of the means, which is closely related to academic success, and plays a big role in differentiation among the students in schools. Various ethnographic works uncovered how the idea of intelligence is constructed and affects everyday activities in school (Bartlett, 2007; LeBlanc, 2017; Lundqvist, 2019). However, no significant work is visible in the context of Bangladesh. An account of the role of intelligence as a construct and its impact in schools would provide a useful framework to understand the process of intelligence being constructed and how actors behind these constructions take part, react and are affected by this process.

This research aims to understand how the idea of intelligence is constructed through various sociocultural elements and beliefs. Using an ethnographic approach, this study will investigate the various elements associated with intelligence in school environments. Additionally, it will explore how diverse belief systems influence perceptions regarding the source of intelligence. Furthermore, the research will examine the impact of intelligence-based classification on students and pedagogical relations in schools.

2. Theoretical Framework

To understand the construction of intelligence, This research uses concepts of 'Figured World' (Holland et al., 2001) and 'Cultural Production Thesis' (Levinson et al., 1996) as its theoretical framework. According to Holland and his colleagues (2001), the 'Figured world' is, "socially and culturally constructed realms of interpretation in which particular characters and actors are recognized, significance is assigned to certain acts and particular outcomes are valued over others." In a figured world, actors can constantly change their strategies and by doing it, also shape their identity. I have also linked identity formation in a 'Figured World' with Goffman's (2022) theory of impression management to show how intelligence is perceived as an identity, practised and desired by the students in classroom settings. Different traits of intelligence often work as a desirable identity marker that students want to achieve. This, in turn, regulates the behaviour and activities of the students in specific ways.

My research is deeply indebted to the 'Cultural Production thesis, epitomised by the works of Holland, Folly and Levinson, which focuses on how ideas of the educated person, smartness, intelligence, genius or other comparable categories that indicate success in schools are the

product of different cultural processes. They point out that every society has some criteria by which a person is identified as more or less knowledgeable as well and there are specific definitions of an intelligent person. Schools do not only produce the idea of 'Intelligent' but also produce the idea of 'Unintelligent'. Schuelka's work (2018) on the Bhutanese schooling system presents an observation on how students are identified as 'Gifted', 'Normal', 'Lazy ', or 'Disabled'. This classification is correlated with local cultural beliefs which produce specific identities of the students as 'abled' or 'disabled.'

One of the major contributions of the cultural production thesis is that it focuses on the active participation of human agency in a constrained structure to show how the cultural production process is shaped by different individuals. I have used these lines of thought in understanding the construction of intelligence in vibrant settings of schools.

3. Methodology

The study was conducted in two suburban Higher Secondary schools, X High School and Y High School, located in Cumilla district, a small city in Bangladesh. Both of the schools receive significant funding from the government. One of the reasons for choosing these schools as my field site was that students from different social backgrounds come to study here and their daily interaction makes the everyday life of the classroom more complex and vibrant. My fieldwork duration was approximately one month, ranging from July to August in 2023. According to Boosntra (2021), classrooms are dynamic cultural and social spaces- where teachers and students actively construct their spheres and negotiate meaning. Throughout my fieldwork, I tried to grasp this dynamic meaning creation process regarding intelligence.

My purpose in this study was to investigate the perceptions of intelligence in the school system and how they work as well as affect everyday life in the classroom. Employing a purposive sampling, a total of 20 informants were interviewed, of them, 11 informants were students from class nine and ten and 9 were teachers. Students with various ranges of academic achievement were taken into consideration in terms of sampling. In-depth interview technique was used along with the classroom observation. All of the interviews were approximately 25-60 minutes long. I have used pseudonyms of the schools and interviewees to protect their privacy.

During fieldwork, I have positioned myself as a researcher in the classroom and tried to avoid any direct interaction in the class. I used a reflexive approach in my research to position myself in the research context and analyse how my experience is influencing my research. To do this, I managed field notes and reflexive notes during my fieldwork and later synthesised these notes with my primary data.

While analysing data, I coded different perspectives on ‘intelligence’ and tried to portray the consensus and the contrasting views of different persons. After the fieldwork, I have transcribed all of the interviews. Then I coded data from interviews and field notes using a thematic approach. This technique helps me to answer different questions that I have posed in my pre-research plan.

4. Elements of Intelligence

In general, intelligence is seen as a cognitive skill which enables a person to learn something more effectively (Mayer, 2000). Most of the discourses and practices around intelligence emphasise the ability to learn effectively by a particular person. Academic success or classroom performance is among the specific markers of intelligence in schools. But in everyday life, intelligence is often associated with many kinds of elements and belief systems apart from cognitive skills. From my fieldwork experience in two different schools, I have noticed that many socio-cultural elements are perceived as the elements of intelligence. In this part, I will cover how intelligence is constructed in the school through different elements.

Academic success is considered a major element of intelligence because the schools put more emphasis on this than any other parameters. Intelligence in Bangladeshi schools heavily relies on the examination system. Results in the exam possibly play the most significant part, as these are used to assess students’ merit in the classroom (Sarker & Chowdhury, 2018). Students are assigned roll numbers based on exam results, creating a strict hierarchy that reflects their academic ranking. If the roll number of a student is 1, that means he or she is the best student and is frequently referred to as the most intelligent. Samir, a student from X High School, said:

“You can measure someone's intelligence by seeing his results. If someone has no intelligence, he cannot study and become a good student. On the contrary, people with high intelligence are often more successful in the exams.”

Sadik, a teacher from the same school, explained:

“We emphasise more on academic results because there are not many indicators to measure one’s intelligence in this school. As you see, guardians are pushing their children for good results. Even if we want to introduce other parameters of intelligence, it is not always possible in the current education system.”

Not just Sadik, but several participants of this research believe that academic success is a prime marker of intelligence. They hold the current educational policies responsible for this emphasis on results.

While academic achievement is a major factor in how intelligence is perceived, it's not the only one. Students and teachers also consider certain behavioural and moral attributes to be markers of intelligence, while others are seen as signs of foolishness. Farida, a teacher from Y High School, said:

“Intelligent are those who always remain quiet in class. They do not do any disturbing activities. They also influence their other classmates to remain silent in the class.”

According to Mahmud, a student,

“I identify intelligent students by their behaviour. I see their actions and way of talking. I think immoral people cannot be intelligent.”

Beyond academic performance, some participants, like Farida and Mahmud, placed significant weight on a range of behavioural factors: punctuality, honesty, kindness, compassion, and even a positive attitude – all seen as contributing to a broader definition of intelligence. Some argue for a link between behavioural and moral attributes and academic success, suggesting that positive behaviours are interrelated to academic achievement.

Another important element of intelligence is communication. Different communication skills, like competent response and strong social network, are often perceived as an identifier of intelligence. According to Riya, a student from class 9 in Y High School,

"For me, intelligence is all about communication. People who can express themselves clearly and connect with others through conversation are the ones I find truly intelligent. That's the kind of person I look for in a friend."

Arifa, a teacher from X High School, said:

“We can't recognize one's intelligence if he or she does not interact in the class. If students do not respond properly to my question, how can I identify their potentiality? ”

Thus, traits like introversion are sometimes perceived as opposed to intelligence. Moreover, students with good communication skills can also showcase their intelligence compared to other students. This also can lead to the overlooking students with less communication skills.

5. Three Types of Beliefs about Intelligence

It was the last day of my fieldwork when I was interviewing Shrabonty, a student from X High School, currently preparing for the SSC- one of the biggest public exams in Bangladesh. Shrabonty was discussing her belief about the sources of intelligence. She said:

“I think a person can be intelligent in many ways. Some people are intelligent by birth. I think family is another factor. If a person comes from an educated family, his or her intelligence will be good enough. I have also seen many people who have become intelligent with their hard work.”

During my fieldwork, I identified a spectrum of beliefs regarding the source of intelligence in Bangladesh. Stemming from the socio-cultural system, factors such as experiential knowledge, morality, and religion shape how people interpret where intelligence comes from. Using a thematic approach, I have categorised these beliefs into three distinct themes: naturalistic belief, personalistic belief, and supernatural belief.

5.1 Naturalistic Belief

The first kind of belief is based on a naturalistic explanation which claims that the intelligence of a person originates from natural factors like genetics and nutrition. Most of the time these types of beliefs outline a simplified relationship between natural factors and intelligence.

Nasim, a student of X High school, said:

“I think one can get intelligence from one's parents. If someone's father or mother is intelligent, it can be transferred to their child. On the other hand, if a mother gets enough nutritious food during her pregnancy, it will improve the brain of the child, as well as intelligence.”

Razzaque, a teacher, shared the same belief, stating,

“My wife is a doctor. I have heard from her that nature has a big impact on our intelligence. If a person comes from a good family, he may have good intelligence by birth.”

Naturalistic belief is also associated with family. A good number of informants who emphasise the natural source of intelligence believe that an intelligent child comes from an intelligent family, thereby connecting a simplified relation between nature and intelligence. Like one of the students from Y High School, Sadik, said:

“Yes, family is the source of intelligence. I have seen from my own life experience that if someone’s parents are teachers or doctors, the person may have good intelligence from birth. As you know, good traits are transformed from parents to their children.”

These quotes exemplify the core ideas of naturalistic beliefs. Informants like Shrabonty, Razzaque, and Sadik believe the primacy of genetics and nutrition as natural determinants of intelligence, often establishing a simplified link between family background and intellectual capacity.

5.2 Personalistic Belief

The second category of belief regarding the source of intelligence is personalistic, which focuses on the individual competency, hard work, and willpower behind one’s intelligence. This kind of belief emphasises an individual's actions in developing the cognitive capacity of a certain person. Some informants I interviewed prioritised personalistic factors over others. Fahima is a student of Y High School, currently studying in class 9. When it came to the discussion of factors behind a person's intelligence, she emphasised the hard work and integrity of the individual. She said:

“I do not think a person can be intelligent by birth. One becomes intelligent by interacting with others, and by learning from surroundings and experience. For example, our teachers teach many things in classes. Not all the students attend those classes properly. If they listen attentively to the lectures, they will be successful in the class.”

This kind of belief is often associated with two types of contrasting views, sameness, and difference. The first view states that all people come into this world with the same intelligence but not all people nurture their intelligence equally. This is the reason why people have different amounts of intelligence. To present this view I am sharing the remarks of Aklima, a teacher from X High School, who said:

“I think everyone has the same level of intelligence, but not everyone uses it in the same way. If someone does hard work, it will improve one's intelligence.”

On the other hand, the contrasting view suggests that people born in this world have different amounts of intelligence, but intelligence can reach its potential when it is nurtured properly. As Riya explained:

“Yes, I believe some people come into this world with special talent. But they must nurture their talent to become intelligent. You can see that some people have talent but due to their economic barriers, they cannot study well. What I want to say is that you must bear your dreams so that you work hard and become an intelligent person.”

Personalistic beliefs differ from the other two categories by emphasising human agency as the source of intelligence, rather than attributing it to fixed entities like genetics or divine intervention. Some personalistic views even posit a link between these fixed entities and human agency, which will be explored in the next section.

5.3 Supernatural Belief

Farhana has been teaching English in a public school for 24 years. She was talking about one of her students named Nayem, who was one of the brightest students in class ten during the year 2003. He was the best in the class and was liked by almost every teacher. But one day, Nayem did ‘something wrong’ with one of his teachers. He had a heated argument in the class, which ended up hurting the teacher’s feelings. The teacher shared his grievances with other teachers. Then, Nayem's results in the final exam were very poor. He failed at 2-3 subjects and never became successful. At some point, Nayem had to drop out. According to Farhana,

“I think it is a curse. If you hurt your elders, you may lose your intelligence. As you know, the position of teacher is after parents.”

Similar to Farhana's perspective, many teachers, students, and guardians hold beliefs that intelligence is a divine gift provided by God, with the power to grant or withhold it. This third category of belief, rooted in supernatural doctrine, emphasises divine intervention as the source of intelligence. It often suggests that God distributes intelligence unevenly. Maria, a student in class 9, said:

“I think there are two types of people. Some people are inherently intelligent. God provides them with a special gift. As you see, Messi is a God-gifted footballer.”

A teacher named Kabir, said:

“I heard this from my elders. You know there is a thing called ‘Prohor’ (a division of time, basically the eighth part of a day) There is the belief that if you have intercourse in

a certain Prohor, it may affect the child. If a pregnant woman goes outside on the new moon, it will have a bad impact on the child.”

Supernatural beliefs of intelligence are mostly based on religious beliefs. These beliefs often come from the same notion that God is the determinator of every trajectory of human life. However, some people connect the supernatural belief with the personalistic view by emphasising the importance of the actions of individuals on their intelligence, as we have seen in Nayeem's case that violating the social norms is believed to be the reason for losing his intelligence.

6. Effect of Classification on Everyday Life at School

“I had a friend named Abhijeet in my previous school. He was not a very good student in the class. For his inactive presence in class, he was often mocked by the teachers and the students. This made him more vulnerable in class and he started to sit on the last bench to stay away from the classroom affairs. I think the treatment he got put mental pressure on him.”

This is what Fahim said about one of his friends. Like this event, the classification based on intelligence and labelling someone as ‘intelligent’ or ‘non-intelligent’ puts pressure on the students and it has an impact on the experience of the students as well as the pedagogy in classrooms. This classification sometimes shapes the selfhood of the students by imposing the societal value system on them, which will be discussed in this part.

Every society has various kinds of classificatory systems and those classifications put a particular person in a hierarchical structure and create a cultural code about how a person should be treated in a specific hierarchy. These classifications can be economic, cultural, social or gendered. Sometimes, economic, social, gendered, and cultural perceptions may work simultaneously in constituting a classification (Holbig & Neckel, 2016). The classification based on intelligence is also closely related to hierarchy as the difference between the ‘intelligent’ and ‘non-intelligent’ student is made keeping these perceptions in mind.

Holbig & Neckel (2016) proposed the idea of ‘Negative Classification’ to refer to “derogatory attributes that social groups direct at each other in their everyday interaction.” These attributes often reveal a normative framework of a particular culture. Referring to someone as ‘non-intelligent,’ ‘foolish’ or ‘dumb’ are the same attributes that can make someone inferior to others. In schools, teachers and students use these terms, which places someone on the lower ladder of school. A teacher named Altaf, said:

“When we get a good student or someone in the class says something outstanding, we praise him. I say that boy is very clever. And when someone says something very wrong in class, we might call him a ‘donkey.’ We use such words unintentionally.”

Using these kinds of derogatory terms to the students is not only limited to the teachers, but students also take part in it. For example, one of my informants, Aklima, explained:

“I call some of my classmates fools. Sometimes if I do not like a student, I also call her a fool.”

The concept of intelligence does not only function as a hierarchical system but it also works as a regulatory system which dictates the students to perform certain behaviours in the school settings. Erving Goffman's renowned work on selfhood (2022) shows a rich insight into the dynamics of human identity within real-time interactions. Goffman thinks that an individual's identity is not a fixed, static construct; rather it is moulded by the ongoing process of impression management in the eyes of others. People are constantly engaged in a complex process of self-presentation, adjusting their behaviour, attire, and other actions to present a particular image or impression that aligns with societal norms and cultural patterns. From my fieldwork experience, I noticed that some students tend to maintain an ‘intelligent self’ in school as it will give them more rewards and include them in the mainstream of the classroom realities. Student of Y High School, Fahima, said:

“I always wanted to be an intelligent person. I want it personally but it is also influenced by my society. If people in my surroundings call me a fool, it would be embarrassing for me. I want to be intelligent because I want to save myself from the scolding of society.”

Thus, society forces an individual to be an intelligent person and the person internalises the behaviour pattern that is associated with intelligence. It leads to the formation of specific kinds of selfhood.

Classification systems based on intelligence also affect the pedagogy of a school. It often limits the effective relationship between teachers and students, impacting the everyday experience in the classroom. During my fieldwork, I have noticed that some of the teachers try to communicate with the students with low grades, but most of the time they end up interacting only with the ‘good’ students, those who often sit in the front of the classroom. This sort of tendency usually limits effective learning for marginalised students in the classroom. A teacher named Arifa said:

“There are three types of students in my class. One type of student is very good and always has good performance in the class. I think they are the most intelligent. On the other hand, some students are average, they are also focused. But there is a section that does not even study and does not answer the teacher's questions in the class.”

These third kinds of students are often outside of the effective learning process. Teachers sometimes refer to them as ‘fools,’ ‘not obedient,’ a person without any goal,’ or ‘spoiled.’ On the other hand, marginalised students face the experience of exclusion in the classroom and these feelings lead to their lack of interaction in the class. Nasif, a student, said:

“I think the teachers only teach the good students. They do not notice students like me. That is why we also do not interact in classes.”

The teacher often provides extra care to the ‘intelligent’ students. Farhana, one of my informants and a teacher, said:

“As you see, when I need to organise a programme for the club, most of the time I prefer good students.”

Thus, intelligence functions as a means of privilege in school and it shapes the everyday experience of the students. Students, who are considered intelligent, are preferred in most academic and extracurricular activities. Due to these preferences and the extra care of the teachers, students, who are entitled as intelligent, can create a strong social (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990) in the school. On the other hand, Students with poor academic results and the tag of ‘non-intelligent’ are often excluded from mainstream practice.

Paolo Freire’s (2014) critical work on pedagogy stated that teachers in the classroom consider students as a ‘blank slate’ and the relationship between teachers and students remains unequal because of the asymmetrical position between teachers and students. He named it the ‘Banking model’ by stating that teachers are the only providers of knowledge in this system and students are passive receivers. But to elaborate on Freire’s argument I would suggest that in the school system, due to the preconception of intelligence, the banking model also does not provide every student with the same amount of knowledge. Students referred to as ‘less intelligent’ are generally alienated from classroom settings.

7. Conclusion

Based on ethnographic research in two different schools in Bangladesh, this research has focused on how the idea of intelligence is constructed by different elements, such as academic success, behavioural and moral elements and communicative elements. People use different parameters like exam results, moral position, honesty and effective communication as markers of intelligence. Through the findings, I uncovered different beliefs about the sources of intelligence, based on naturalistic, personalistic and supernatural preconceptions. These elements and beliefs altogether shape perceptions of intelligence, which vary from person to person. Naturalistic

belief is based on factors like genetics and nutrition, whereas personalistic belief emphasises the action and willpower of an individual as the primary source of intelligence. Furthermore, supernatural belief based on religious assumption focuses on the primacy of divine interventions as the source of intelligence.

The paper has aimed to look deeper into the impact of classification based on intelligence in schools. I have not only disclosed the mental impact of this classification but also drawn a link between the intelligence construct, regulating behaviour and formation of specific kinds of selfhood. Intelligence is often correlated to the specific qualities and behaviours in school systems and this correlation posits some kinds of quality and behavioural traits as expected and others as non-desired. A person who possesses some specific traits which are correlated to the ‘non-intelligent’ is often denounced by the teachers and students in the classroom. On the other hand, some students strategically maintain an intelligent self by possessing certain attributes. The classification process also affects the pedagogy of schools as the differentiation based on intelligence creates a situation where some students are preferred over others. This in turn creates unequal relations among the students.

This study helps to further discover the relationship between intelligence construction and everyday experience in schools. Through a culturally embedded analysis, my research contributes to the current discourse of pedagogy and inclusive education by investigating the role of different sociocultural ideas and beliefs in everyday academic activities of the school system.

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